

How Third Parties Make Campaign Promises: An Analysis of United States Presidential Politics

A THESIS

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By

Thomas Gala-Garza

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Advised by Kenneth Lowande

Abstract

This thesis compares campaign promise statements made by major-party and third-party United States presidential candidates from 2000 to 2024. Using an original hand-coded dataset of 1,344 promises drawn from 109 campaign materials across 64 candidacies, it examines differences in promise frequency, specificity, and issue emphasis. I find that third-party candidates make approximately 42 percent fewer promises per campaign appearance than major-party candidates, controlling for event format, medium, election year, and candidate demographics. On any single measure of specificity, I find no significant difference between major- and third-party promises, though third-party promises are less likely to satisfy multiple specificity criteria simultaneously once speech length is held constant. Party-level analysis shows that major- and third-party candidates emphasize different issue areas, with each third party displaying a distinct issue profile. Pooled Shannon entropy indicates that third parties collectively cover a broader range of topics than major parties. However, individual third-party candidate platforms are not narrower in issue breadth than those of individual major-party candidates once promise count is controlled for. These findings suggest that third-party presidential candidates are not best understood as vague or underdeveloped alternatives to major-party candidates. Instead, they function as agenda-differentiating actors who intervene in presidential politics by bringing neglected issues to the forefront and showing voters their alternate priorities, even when they are unlikely to win office.

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Introduction

Since 1852, United States presidential elections have formed a two-party system in which two major parties, currently Republicans and Democrats, dominate electoral competition and results. The limited extent of third-party success is evident in their failure to win a presidential election for over 100 years. In the wake of this fact, third-party campaigns persist. They continue to run, attract support, and shape political debate. Research on electoral systems helps explain why this pattern endures, emphasizing how plurality voting pushes competition toward two dominant parties and places smaller parties at a disadvantage (Riker 1982). At the same time, scholarship on American third parties shows that these candidates can still matter by expressing protest, drawing support from dissatisfied voters, and raising issues that major parties may not emphasize (Abramson et al. 1995; Burden 2005; Koch 2003).

Third parties' unique circumstances and goals shape their strategy as fundamentally differing from that of major parties. They may run not to win immediately but instead to influence the agenda and set up their future success. Hence, their structural disadvantage also informs how third parties communicate with voters. Candidates facing unfavorable conditions may strategically narrow their message to a small number of issues from which they can benefit (Vavreck 2009), and limited media access further constrains how many issues they can raise in a given appearance (Hopmann et al. 2012). Work on party competition suggests that parties do not compete only by taking different positions, but also by deciding which issues to emphasize and which issues to leave aside (Petrocik 1996; Damore 2004; Dolezal et al. 2014). This dynamic is especially relevant for third-party candidates, who may have more incentive to differentiate themselves through selective emphasis and issue entrepreneurship than through direct

competition on the same terms as major-party candidates (Meyer and Miller 2015; Hobolt and De Vries 2015).

Most promise research asks whether promises matter, whether voters remember them, or whether winners fulfill them. It says much less about promise-making, and how that differs between major-party and third-party presidential candidates, especially as it pertains to promise quantity, specificity, and issue emphasis. Existing work on campaign promises has paid particular attention to promise fulfillment and to differentiating real promises from vague rhetoric (Royed 1996; Bonilla 2024). Related work also suggests that third-party candidates in particular may need specific promises both to build credibility with skeptical voters and to pressure major parties into responding to their issues (Adams and Merrill 2006). This thesis compares major- and third-party presidential candidates' campaign promise statements from 2000 to 2024, coding their language to then examine what types of promises are made, how many are made, and how specific they are.

This argument contributes to several literatures. First, it extends research on campaign promises by comparing promise-making across party types rather than focusing, as prior work has, only on whether promises are fulfilled or how specific they are (Royed 1996; Bonilla 2024). It also contributes to scholarship on third-party politics by showing that third-party candidates may be rhetorically distinct without being individually narrower in platform scope (Abramson et al. 1995; Burden 2005; Koch 2003). Finally, it contributes to broader work on party competition by suggesting that third-party candidates function as agenda differentiators within presidential campaigns, as they emphasize issues that diverge from major-party agendas (Petrocik 1996; Damore 2004; Dolezal et al. 2014; Meyer and Miller 2015; Hobolt and De Vries 2015).

The next section of the thesis reviews literature on third-party electoral incentives, campaign promises and specificity, and party competition through issue emphasis and platform breadth. I then develop three hypotheses about how major- and third-party candidates should differ in promise frequency, specificity, and issue emphasis. After describing the data and methods, I present the empirical results and conclude by discussing what they suggest about the role of third-party candidates in U.S. presidential politics.

Theoretical Foundations

Hypothesis 1: Third-Party Electoral Incentives and Promise Count

French political theorist Maurice Duverger laid the framework for understanding the plight of third parties with Duverger's law, which states that "The simple-majority single ballot system favors the two-party system" (Riker 1982, 754)¹. According to Duverger's law, plurality is a sufficient condition for a system where two parties emerge as dominants, putting smaller third parties at a disadvantage.

In addition, major parties actively work to keep third parties from success. Part of all party strategy is to "limit competition for votes", and the "party in power, to the extent it is able, will try to limit the entry of other parties into the electoral arena" (Lewis-Beck and Squire, 1995, 420). Third parties thus become the target of attack via ballot exclusion. To keep the number of names on presidential ballots from growing too large, states set "particular access requirements", such as certain signature counts, for third parties to appear (Lewis-Beck and Squire, 1995, 419). Acting on their motive to block competition, major parties find it the easiest to dedicate resources towards increasing these barriers. Crucially, "no Democrat or Republican presidential ballot exclusions have occurred in recent times", highlighting major parties' shared interest in avoiding competition to the point of implicit collusion (Lewis-Beck and Squire, 1995, 420).

While "the number of candidates drops" as a result of ballot exclusion, the technique affects "the number of candidates on the ballot but not their vote totals" (Burden 2007, 669).

Although many weaker third parties fail to appear on the ballot, those already strong enough to

¹ The "simple-majority single ballot" terminology is misleading and actually refers to plurality voting, where "the unique winner is the single candidate with the most votes" (Riker 1982, 754).

withstand ballot regulations are largely unaffected. This means structural limitations alone cannot fully explain why third parties consistently fail to win.

The other half of the explanation is the “psychological factor” of voters’ inclination to vote against third parties (Riker 1982, 762). Voters first attempt to determine “what party he believes will benefit him most”, but they also consider “whether this party has any chance of winning” (Riker 1982, 762). If a third party is not expected to win, then a vote for that party is essentially a ‘wasted’ vote. The rational decision is instead to vote for the larger party which has higher odds of winning, even though it is only the voter’s second choice. The pattern of “sophisticated voting” occurs in “a large amount” (Riker 1982, 764) among two-party systems such as the US, where it affected “American third-party and independent presidential candidates from William Wirt in 1832 through H. Ross Perot in 1992” (Abramson et al., 1995, 355).

While third parties are often cast aside out of rationality or fear, they continue to gain support, as voters often select third parties to “send a message to political elites” in “states where the Democratic or Republican (candidate) is likely to win” (Burden 2005, 606). This message takes the form of a vote but is in effect a “protest against the major party duopoly” (Burden 2005, 606). “Distrust of the national government” was found to be a strong predictor of whether a voter would select third-party candidates George Wallace, John Anderson and Ross Perot (Peterson and Wrighton, 1998, 17). Perot embodied the idea with the campaign slogan “don’t waste your vote for politics as usual” (Abramson et al., 1995, 353).

With the outcome effectively decided already, the risk of a wasted vote is little to none, so voters become “liberated to support her candidate without fear of changing the outcome” (Burden 2005, 606). This phenomenon can cause third-party candidates’ “vote share to exceed

the final poll numbers”, letting their final support be more reflective of actual voter preference (Burden 2005, 612).

Scholars disagree on when and how this cynicism is introduced to voters. Some believe that, rather than previously held distrust leading voters to choose third parties, the parties themselves cultivate this distrust during their campaigns. Third parties’ position as “the ultimate outsiders” may imprint their candidates with government distrust (Koch 2003, 49). As they “mentor citizens” to “adopt their same ideas and platform”, they spread their distrust to voters who did not originally feel that way (Koch 2003, 49). No matter which way protest votes are manufactured, the result is a voter base concerned less with winning the election and more with expressing discontent.

These dynamics change how third-party candidates approach their campaigns. Faced with the unlikelihood of winning, third-party representatives instead become “politicians who buy a future” (Riker 1982, 764), steadily growing voter bases over time so that they may eventually become large enough to usurp a major party’s place. Even the Republican Party was once a third party, ultimately displacing the Whigs to cement itself as a major party (Abramson et al. 1995, 349). Contemporary third parties hope to one day replicate this success through consistent presence at elections.

The lack of electoral viability suggests campaign rhetoric may serve less to outline a comprehensive governing agenda and more to differentiate themselves with their mere presence, shaping the terms of future political debate. Vavreck (2009) argues that candidates facing unfavorable structural conditions, what she calls “insurgent” candidates, must strategically narrow their message. She claims insurgent candidates “have to find something else to talk about”, moving from popular issues such as the economy “onto an issue from which they can

benefit" (Vavreck 2009, 32). The "choice of insurgent issue is critical," meaning the candidate must pick a single dimension of competition and concentrate on it rather than ranging across many topics (Vavreck 2009, 33). The strategic choice to narrow campaign scope inherently limits the number of promises a candidate may make in any single appearance.

Although Vavreck is describing major-party candidates whose platforms are disadvantaged by the economy, the underlying logic applies even more strongly to third-party candidates, who are structurally disadvantaged in nearly every election regardless of economic conditions. This disadvantage is compounded by the media environment. In multiparty systems, "the more relevant parties have more success" in getting covered by journalists and the news on their preferred issues (Hopmann et al. 2012, 173). Depending on how the media perceives the significance of candidates and their agendas, they may "open the gates wider or close them more tightly" (Hopmann et al. 2012, 177). If less-relevant parties struggle to pass through these media gates, third-party candidates have fewer opportunities to communicate with voters, incentivizing them to fill that time with fewer but more memorable campaign promises. Taken together, the dynamics of reduced electoral viability and limited media access provide a basis for expecting third-party candidates to make fewer promise statements per speech than their major-party counterparts.

***Hypothesis 1:** Third-party presidential candidates make fewer promise statements per speech than major-party presidential candidates.*

Hypothesis 2: Campaign Promises and Specificity

A campaign promise can be defined as “a position statement on a policy issue that explicitly indicates an action a candidate will take if elected to office or identifies a political outcome as a result of the candidate’s election” (Bonilla 2024, 6). Many academics first identify “potential pledges”, or “statements that can be separated from descriptions of past or current situations, evaluations and critics of past governments, and general rhetorical statements” (Naurin 2013, 33-34). A potential pledge becomes an actual pledge if it includes “a description of what actions will be taken or what goal will be strived towards” (Naurin 2013, 34). Any statement with a goal that one could equally argue was reached or not reached is “too vague or vague-laden to be considered a real pledge” (Royed 1996, 79). Instead, these goals are “rhetorical statements” which are “untestable” (Royed 1996, 80).

In her 1996 study, Royed placed potential promises into three categories: ones where “definite action is promised, and determining fulfillment is clear-cut”, ones where “definite action is promised... but testing is difficult”, and ones where “it is impossible to determine objectively whether or not the promise has been fulfilled” (Royed 1996, 79-80). The latter are reclassified as rhetorical statements, but the former two are both still viewed as promises. Here, specificity acts as the divider between categories. Any promise that is difficult to test has an implied lack of specificity that makes the promise a rhetorical statement.

Analyzing promise specificity is important for several reasons. Firstly, more specific promises are easier to compare to actual implemented policy to determine whether it has been kept or not, which increases democratic accountability. Second, more specific promises give voters more concrete information to understand a candidate’s priorities and goals, distinguishing them from other candidates. Finally, specificity has the power to distinguish real commitments

candidates make from symbolic rhetoric, providing a clear, consistent standard for coding promise data.

One might expect third-party voters, as primarily protest voters, to be indifferent to policy specificity. However, Abramson et al. (1995) show that third-party supporters have made genuine candidate-level evaluations: Wallace "won the votes of 84 percent of the voters who ranked him highest," a retention rate that reflects real candidate attachment rather than directionless protest (Abramson et al. 1995, 360). Even voters most pressured by what Abramson et al. call "the wasted vote argument" were still weighing candidates on substantive dimensions (Abramson et al. 1995, 363). If third-party voters are evaluating candidates at all, then candidates who offer only vague promises risk being unable to distinguish themselves and further their own previously established goal of future agenda-setting.

This finding matters because specificity is how candidates without institutional backing establish credibility. Major-party candidates can rely on party brand and incumbency to signal competence to voters. Third-party candidates have none of these resources and must instead demonstrate credibility through promises. Voters, when evaluating trust in candidates, differentiate between kept, partially kept, and broken promises. This differentiation depends on promises being specific enough to compare to implemented policy (Bonilla 2024). Without specificity, this trust-building fails to function. Hence, for third-party candidates trying to build trust from scratch, making specific and testable promises is one of the few tools available for convincing skeptical voters that they are serious.

Specificity also serves a second, structural function for third-party candidates: it is the mechanism through which they force their issues onto the agenda in the long term. Even a party with "no realistic chance of winning" can pressure major parties to reposition their agendas, as

long as the third-party agenda is specific enough to warrant a response (Adams and Merrill 2006, 403). The mere presence of a third party “motivates the major parties to propose policies that are much more divergent than without the third party” (Adams and Merrill 2006, 403). This pressure depends entirely on the third party having an identifiable party position. Having only a vague platform gives major parties nothing to respond to, but a specific one forces them to move. Third-party candidates therefore face two incentives to be specific that major-party candidates do not: to build trust with voters and to influence the agenda with major parties. Due to this, I hypothesize third-party campaign promises are more specific than those made by major-party candidates.

***Hypothesis 2:** Third-party presidential candidates’ promise statements are more specific than those of major-party presidential candidates.*

Hypothesis 3: Issue Emphasis

However, specificity is only one feature of campaign promises, and they can vary in several other ways across campaign events. Different candidates might make promises on different issues and cover a different variety of those issues. For this reason, comparing major- and third-party promises requires not only analyzing specificity, but also issue emphasis. This allows for a more complete understanding of how different types of candidates structure their promises.

Other research shows how candidates from different parties can vary the content of their promises. Work on saliency theory and selective emphasis argues that parties compete not only by having different positions on issues, but by choosing which issues to highlight. Saliency theory is a model of party competition whose "central claim... is that parties compete by selective

issue emphasis rather than by direct confrontation" (Dolezal et al. 2014, 57). Because "parties hardly ever talk about their opponents in election campaigns," they must draw attention instead to "issues that are advantageous for themselves" (Dolezal et al. 2014, 58). In this model, the ultimate goal for candidates is to "achieve a strategic advantage" by centering the election around "problems which reflect owned issues" (Petrocik 1996, 828).

Issue ownership theory explains the origin of these strategic advantages. It claims that "parties hold reputations for their ability to handle certain issues", which give candidates "credibility over issues associated with their party" (Damore 2004, 391). This credibility, effectively serving as ownership, is generally thought of via two distinct dimensions: "competence issue ownership", or "parties' perceived capacity to competently handle and 'resolve' particular issues", and "associative issue ownership", which does not require competence and is instead "spontaneous identification between some parties and some issues" (Walgrave et al. 2015, 779). Because "voters are more likely to support the party owning the issue at the heart of the election campaign" (Geys 2012, 407), candidates are incentivized to make the issues they own appear most important.

Understanding these dynamics is essential for analyzing the campaign behavior of third parties in the US. The concept of niche parties, which include third parties, stems from salience theory, defined as "parties emphasizing a limited set of new issues that do not coincide with the predominant economic left-right division" (Meyer and Miller 2015, 259). More simply put, a niche party is "a party emphasizing other policy areas than its competitors do" (Meyer and Miller 2015, 260).

Theoretical research on niche parties suggests they have "little incentive to behave strategically" because they "advance a very narrow set of issues" and believe "they will be

unable to boost their support by emphasising non-niche issues" (Elias et al. 2015, 842).

However, campaign data reveals that parties do not always strictly adhere only to issues they own, as candidates frequently "choose to trespass on issues associated with the opposition's party" (Damore 2004, 391). For example, mainstream parties often attempt to combat third-party competitors by "taking a tougher stance on issues related to immigration and integration" (Geys 2012, 410). This suggests that differences between major- and third-party campaign promises may appear not only in how promises are phrased, but also through the policy areas candidates choose to emphasize.

To differentiate themselves and make promises focusing on different policy areas, niche candidates may act as issue entrepreneurs. Through issue entrepreneurship, parties focus on "issues that have been largely ignored in party competition", adopting a position that is "substantially different from the mainstream status quo" (Hobolt and De Vries 2015, 2). Acting as "challenger parties", niche parties can use this method to cause "electoral threats to mainstream parties" (Williams and Hunger 2022, 545). In the end, by making new issues matter more to the public, niche parties can pull voters away from major parties.

Research on selective emphasis suggests that parties compete not only by adopting positions, but by deciding which issues to bring to the forefront. This is particularly relevant for third-party candidates, who cannot easily compete with major parties by simply reproducing their issue agendas. To gain visibility and support, outsider candidates are more likely to emphasize issues that major-party candidates neglect. Related work on issue ownership further suggests that parties benefit from emphasizing issues that align with their identities or where competitors appear weak or inattentive. For third-party candidates, this implies that rhetorical differentiation may take the form of issue selection as much as policy position. Because of this,

my third hypothesis is that third-party presidential candidates emphasize different issues in their promise statements than major-party presidential candidates.

***Hypothesis 3:** The distribution of promises across issues differs significantly between individual major- and third-party candidates.*

Summary

Table 1: The three hypotheses for consideration on third-party promise-making strategy

Hypothesis	Text
1	Third-party presidential candidates make fewer promise statements per speech than major-party presidential candidates.
2	Third-party presidential candidates' promise statements are more specific than those of major-party presidential candidates.
3	The distribution of promises across issues differs significantly between individual major- and third-party candidates.

The literature suggests that third-party presidential candidates operate under electoral and strategic incentives that differ from those of major-party candidates. Because campaign promises serve as signals of intended action and political priorities, those incentive differences should be visible not only in whether candidates make promises, but also in how often they do so, how specific those promises are, and what issues they emphasize. The hypotheses above translate these expectations into testable differences between major- and third-party promise statements.

Methods

Data Collection

Promise statements have been compiled in an original hand-coded database, created on Google Sheets and published via Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19243497>. Each row in this spreadsheet corresponds to a single promise statement. Promises originate from United States presidential candidates for the election years 2000, 2004, 2008, 2012, 2016, 2020, and 2024. This time frame was selected for ease of locating campaign materials, which are defined as sources of campaign promises made by candidates to a public audience.

Each statement includes a link to its source and a transcript. Video speeches and town halls were sourced from video websites YouTube and C-SPAN, radio interviews from YouTube, and articles from news sites such as CNN. When transcripts of these materials were not already available, such as via transcription website rev.com, videos were downloaded and transcribed using the otter.ai website, which generates transcripts using artificial intelligence. Otter.ai transcripts are linked for most promise statements. Because this technology is prone to inaccuracies, when necessary, transcripts have been edited against the actual audio for accuracy when included in the database.

In total, 109 materials and 1,344 promises were catalogued across seven election periods, from 64 candidacies. Of these, 8 repeat candidates contributed 10 repeat candidacies, with 6 candidates running twice and 2 candidates running three times. This leaves 54 unique candidates. 796, or 59.2%, of promises come from major parties (the Republican or Democratic parties). 548, or 40.8%, come from third parties (all other parties). 15 unique third parties, as well as independent candidates, are represented.

Table 2: Summary statistics for the promise database

	Major Party	Third Party	Total
Candidates	18	36	54
Candidacies	23	41	64
Campaign materials	42	67	109
Total promises	796	548	1344
Promises per material			
Mean	19	8.2	12.3
Standard deviation	10.2	7.1	9.9
Median	17	6	10
Range	5–61	1–35	1–61
Materials per candidate			
Mean	2.3	1.9	2
Range	1–6	1–5	1–6
Candidates with < 5 promises	0	8	8

The distribution of promises across candidacies varied considerably. Among major-party candidacies, the most prolific was Al Gore in 2000, with 90 promises across his materials, followed by Nikki Haley in 2024 (56) and John Kerry in 2004 (54). The least prolific major-party candidacy was Asa Hutchinson in 2024, with 5 promises. Among third-party candidacies, the most prolific was Jill Stein in 2016, with 54 promises. The least prolific third-party candidacies, including Alyson Kennedy in 2016, Kanye West in 2020, and Róger Calero in 2008, each made only 1 promise. When aggregated across election cycles, Donald Trump made the most total promises of any candidate (133 across three cycles), while Jill Stein made the most of any third-party candidate (97 across three cycles).

Each statement also includes various metadata: the format and medium of the material and the name, gender, age, race/ethnicity and party of the candidate. Promises appeared in the

mediums of live television or radio, as well as pre-recorded video or articles. In addition, they appeared in the following formats: Speeches (including campaign acceptance speeches, stump speeches, rallies and addresses); town hall discussions; debates and interviews.

Table 3: Candidacies by election year

Election Year	Major Party	Third Party	Total
2000	2	0	2
2004	2	4	6
2008	2	5	7
2012	2	6	8
2016	3	8	11
2020	2	8	10
2024	10	10	20
Total	23	41	64

During earlier election cycles, third-party campaign materials are sparser, with none from the 2000 election. The number and variety of third-party campaigns increase with more contemporary election cycles.

Table 4: Descriptive statistics for promise metadata

	Major Party	Third Party	Total
Format			
Speech	37	21	58
Interview	1	43	44
Debate	0	3	3
Town Hall	4	1	5
Medium			
Television	38	40	78
Video	0	18	18
Article	4	5	9
Radio	0	5	5
Demographics			
Male	20	31	51
Female	3	10	13
White	19	31	50
Black	4	5	9
Hispanic	0	5	5
Age (mean)	61.3	58.9	59.8

These counts are at the candidacy level (N = 64).

Major-party materials contained an average of 19 promises, compared to 8.2 for third-party materials. The distribution of materials across formats differed substantially between party types. 37 of 42 major-party materials were speeches, whereas 43 of 67 third-party materials were interviews. Only one major-party material was an interview. The three debate materials come from different candidates' contributions to the same event, in which they made three different sets of promises for their candidacies. This same difference in distribution persisted for mediums: while television was common for both party types, all 18 video materials and all 5 radio materials came from third-party candidates. Demographically, the sample skewed male (51 of 64 candidacies) and white (50 of 64). All 5 Hispanic candidacies were third-party, and female candidates were proportionally more common among third parties (10 of 41) than major parties (3 of 23). The average candidate age was similar across party types, at 61.3 for major-party and 58.9 for third-party candidacies.

The 1,344 promises in the database were categorized across 36 issues listed in Appendix I. The most frequently addressed category was Healthcare (166 promises, 12.4%), followed by Education (126, 9.4%), Taxes (117, 8.7%), and Environment & energy (107, 8.0%).

Table 5: How many promises appeared under each issue topic

Topic	Promise Count	Percentage
Healthcare	166	12.4%
Education	126	9.4%
Taxes	117	8.7%
Environment & energy	107	8.0%
Immigration & border security	87	6.5%
Government spending, debt & reform	76	5.7%
Foreign policy & diplomacy	58	4.3%
Infrastructure	53	3.9%
Wages & workers' rights	49	3.6%
Military & defense	44	3.3%
Jobs & employment	43	3.2%
Social Security & retirement	36	2.7%
Crime & criminal justice	36	2.7%
Wars & military intervention	33	2.5%
Drug policy	32	2.4%
Abortion & reproductive rights	31	2.3%
Economy (general)	30	2.2%
Elections & campaign finance	29	2.2%
Trade & tariffs	28	2.1%
Civil liberties, privacy & free speech	22	1.6%
Housing	20	1.5%
Welfare & poverty	19	1.4%
LGBTQ+ rights	14	1.0%
Gun policy	14	1.0%
Racial justice & civil rights	13	1.0%
Childcare & family policy	12	0.9%
Cost of living & inflation	9	0.7%
Anti-DEI & anti-woke policy	9	0.7%
Courts & judicial appointments	8	0.6%
General governance & leadership	7	0.5%
Culture, faith & values	6	0.4%
Wealth inequality & corporate power	5	0.4%
Veterans affairs	2	0.1%
Food & agriculture	1	0.1%
Space & science	1	0.1%
Disaster response	1	0.1%

Data Coding

Any statement in a presidential campaign material is a potential promise if it “can be separated from descriptions of past or current situations, evaluations and critics of past governments, and general rhetorical statements” (Naurin 2013, 33-34). A potential promise

becomes an actual promise if it includes “a description of what actions will be taken or what goal will be strived towards” (Naurin 2013, 34). Only actual promises appear in the database.

Statements of opinion, general criticism of opponents, and vague expressions of values without a description or goal were not included.

Common phrases that may indicate, but are not necessary for, a promise statement being present include: "I promise"; "I want"; "I will"; "We will"; "I'm going to"; "We're going to"; "I pledge to you"; "When I am elected"; "My plan is".

A statement may be one or more sentences that capture a distinct commitment to some action or goal. If a single statement contains more than one commitment, it was coded as a separate promise. Repeated statements of the same promise in the same material were generally counted once unless they introduced substantively new content. Repeated statements across multiple materials were counted each time. When a statement could fit multiple issues, it was coded based on the primary area emphasized.

For example, the following are promise statements found in the database about the issue of taxes:

- “The first tax I would look to eliminate would be the federal income tax.” (Jo Jorgenson, Libertarian Party, 2020)
- “Wall Street, corporations, and the super rich are going to start paying their fair share of taxes.” (Hillary Clinton, Democratic Party, 2016)
- “While Biden is pushing the largest tax hike in American history, I will make the Trump tax cuts, again, the biggest ever in history. We’re going to make them permanent.” (Donald Trump, Republican Party, 2024).

Once promise statements were transcribed and transferred to the database, they were then hand-coded according to: a) the issue highlighted, from the list in Appendix I, and b) three binary variables:

1. Policy/Action: whether the action to be taken or goal to be strived towards addresses the implementation or adjustment of a specific policy or action to be taken, or not taken.
2. Outcome: whether the statement includes a goal that will be strived towards.
3. Timeline: whether the action to be taken or goal to be strived towards includes a timeline or end date for reaching that goal.

The presence of these elements in a given statement was used to determine the degree of specificity of the statement. A more specific promise contains more of these signifiers and a less specific promise contains fewer of them. By the definition of a promise above, all database entries contain either a Policy/Action or Outcome. Some may include both, and some with one or both may also include a Timeline. The number of criteria each statement satisfies is tracked in the database.

The following are randomly selected examples of promise statements for each possible combination of specificity criteria, along with how those examples were coded:

Policy/Action

- “In a new term, I will ensure every poor county in America has a community or rural health center.” (George Bush, Republican Party, 2004)
 - Policy/Action: “every poor county in America has a community or rural health center”

- “We need police commissions that are selected by the people, with the power to hire and fire the police chiefs.” (Howie Hawkins, Green Party, 2020)

- Policy/Action: “police commissions that are selected by the people”

Outcome

- “We want equality for lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender people.” (Peta Lindsay, Peace and Freedom Party, 2012)

- Outcome: “equality for lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender people”

- “We will honor—we will honor equal rights, and we will fight for an equal day's pay for an equal day's work.” (Al Gore, Democratic Party, 2000)

- Outcome: “an equal day's pay for an equal day's work”

Policy/Action and Timeline

- “I will immediately sign a new executive order to cut federal funding for any school pushing critical race theory, transgender insanity, and either racial, sexual, or political content on our children.” (Donald Trump, Republican Party, 2024)

- Policy/Action: “a new executive order...”

- Timeline: “immediately”

- “We're pledging to submit a balanced budget to Congress in the first 100 days.” (Gary Johnson, Libertarian Party, 2016)

- Policy/Action: “submit a balanced budget to Congress”

- Timeline: “in the first 100 days”

Outcome and Timeline

- “And patterned after the Peace Corps in AmeriCorps, I launched the Climate Corps to put 20,000 young people to work in the forefront of our clean energy future. I’ll triple that number in a decade.” (Joe Biden, Democratic Party, 2024)
 - Outcome: “triple that number”
 - Timeline: “in a decade”
- “I’m running to make sure that by the end of the decade, more of our citizens hold a college degree than any other nation on Earth.” (Barack Obama, Democratic Party, 2012)
 - Outcome: “more of our citizens hold a college degree than any other nation on Earth”
 - Timeline: “by the end of the decade”

Policy/Action and Outcome

- “You can have public schools, but they gotta be user fee based, not tax based, so that they are competing on an equal basis with private and home schooling, who don't have to pay twice.” (Joel Skousen, Constitution Party, 2024)
 - Policy/Action: “user fee based, not tax based [public schools]”
 - Outcome: “[public schools] are competing on an equal basis with private and home schooling”
- “Eliminating automatic birthright citizenship would also significantly help the budgetary situation of the United States and of several other states.” (Virgil Goode, Constitution Party, 2012)
 - Policy/Action: “Eliminating automatic birthright citizenship”
 - Outcome: “significantly help the budgetary situation of the United States and of several other states”

Policy/Action, Outcome and Timeline

- “On our day one in office, our administration will legalize cannabis, for starters, to help take the rug out from under the drug cartels, which are forcing people here to flee.” (Jill Stein, Green Party, 2024)
 - Policy/Action: “legalize cannabis”
 - Outcome: “to help take the rug out from under the drug cartels”
 - Timeline: “On our day one in office”

- “We can cut our oil imports in half by 2020 and support more than 600,000 new jobs in natural gas alone.” (Barack Obama, Democratic Party, 2012)
 - Policy/Action: “cut our oil imports in half”
 - Outcome: “support more than 600,000 new jobs in natural gas alone”
 - Timeline: “by 2020”

Analysis 1 – Promise Count

After coding, the dataset was used for descriptive and comparative analysis between major-party and third-party promises. The first model used simply examines the number of promises made in each campaign material. Because the dependent variable is a count, this analysis uses a Poisson regression, which is designed specifically for count data and ensures results are always modeled as non-negative numbers of promises. The independent variable is the binary of whether a candidate belongs to a major or third party. The control variables include speech format, medium, election year, and speaker gender, race/ethnicity, and age. Standard errors are clustered by candidate to account for the fact that some candidates appear in multiple election cycles. Material length is measured as the natural log of word count to account for the diminishing marginal effect of additional words in longer materials.

Table 6: Poisson regression table predicting promise counts in campaign material²

Variable	Coefficient	Clustered SE	z-statistic	p-value
(Intercept)	0.9353	0.7370	1.269	0.2044
Third party	-0.5470	0.2005	-2.728	0.0064**
Log word count	0.3243	0.0847	3.830	0.0001***
Format: Interview	-0.5660	0.2094	-2.702	0.0069**
Format: Town Hall	-0.5772	0.1902	-3.034	0.0024**
Format: Debate	0.0551	0.2580	0.214	0.8308
Medium: Article	0.2037	0.2273	0.896	0.3703
Medium: Radio	-0.6305	0.2983	-2.114	0.0345*
Medium: Video	-0.3116	0.2149	-1.450	0.1470
Election year: 2004	-0.2979	0.3236	-0.921	0.3573
Election year: 2008	-0.4606	0.3855	-1.195	0.2322
Election year: 2012	-0.3659	0.3833	-0.955	0.3398
Election year: 2016	-0.6219	0.3560	-1.747	0.0806†
Election year: 2020	-0.2481	0.3359	-0.739	0.4600
Election year: 2024	-0.5969	0.3357	-1.778	0.0754†
Gender: Female	0.4806	0.1516	3.169	0.0015**
Race/Ethnicity: Black	-0.3510	0.2422	-1.450	0.1472
Race/Ethnicity: Hispanic	0.0320	0.2039	0.157	0.8753
Age	-0.0056	0.0052	-1.074	0.2829

N = 109 campaign materials. Clusters = 54 candidates.

† $p < 0.10$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

The Poisson regression predicting the number of promise statements per campaign material found that third-party candidates make significantly fewer promises per speech than major-party candidates, even after controlling for speech length. The coefficient on the third-

² Where regression tables appear, the following variables are used as reference categories: Major Party; Format: Speech; Medium: Television; Election year 2000; Male; White.

party variable is -0.547 with a clustered standard error of 0.201 and a p-value of 0.006 . To make this result interpretable, I used the model to simulate expected promise counts for two hypothetical candidates who are identical in almost every respect: both giving a televised speech of median length in 2016, and both white males of average age, except that one is major-party and the other third-party.

Table 7: Simulated expected promise counts by party type (95% confidence intervals)

Party	Estimate	Lower	Upper
Major Party	16.19	11.38	22.38
Third Party	9.47	6.01	14.12

Expected Promise Count by Party Type

Poisson model, controlling for speech length, format, medium, year, demographics

Figure 1: Box plot of simulated expected promise counts by party type (95% confidence intervals)

Under these conditions, the model predicts that a major-party candidate would make approximately 16 promises in a campaign material, compared to approximately 9.5 for the average third-party candidate. The 95 percent confidence interval for the major-party prediction is 11.4 to 22.4 promises, and for the third-party prediction, 6.0 to 14.1. Material length, measured as the natural log of word count, is included as a control variable and is itself a strong predictor of promise count (coefficient = 0.324, $p < 0.001$), confirming that longer materials produce more promises. Crucially, the third-party coefficient remains significant even after accounting for this effect, indicating that the difference in promise frequency between party types is not simply a byproduct of third-party materials being shorter.

Among the control variables, speech format had the most consistent effect. Relative to speeches, interviews are associated with significantly fewer promises (coefficient = -0.566 , $p = 0.007$), as are town halls (coefficient = -0.577 , $p = 0.002$). Medium was largely insignificant, except for radio, which was associated with fewer promises relative to television (coefficient = -0.631 , $p = 0.035$). Among demographic controls, the female coefficient was positive and significant (coefficient = 0.481 , $p = 0.002$), indicating that female candidates in the sample made more promises per speech on average, though this should be interpreted cautiously given the small number of female candidacies.

Interpretation

This result confirms the first hypothesis by showing third parties make fewer promise statements per material than major parties. It is consistent with the expectation that major-party candidates, being seen as more viable as actual governing figures, have stronger incentives to showcase broader governing agendas. Voters, the media, and party organizations all expect these

nominees to demonstrate their ability to govern across the full spectrum of policy issues.

Likewise, campaign materials act as an opportunity to do so. The number of promises they make reflects this increased pressure.

By contrast, third-party candidates operate under different constraints. Because they are less likely to win office immediately, they may utilize rhetoric more selectively, focusing on a small number of promises instead of trying to present a full governing program during every speech. This interpretation is consistent with the literature's idea that outsider candidates use campaigns to differentiate themselves and shape future political debate, rather than focus on short-term wins. The lower promise count third parties have can be seen as evidence of this strategic prioritization, focusing on a targeted set of issues with fewer statements made.

These results held even after controlling for differences in speech format and medium, which is important because third-party candidates tend to appear in different types of events than major-party candidates. Third-party candidates were more often represented in interviews and smaller media formats rather than large-scale rallies, and the models found that interviews and town halls are independently associated with fewer promises relative to rallies. The fact that third-party status remained a significant predictor even after accounting for this suggests a real difference in campaign strategy, not just a side effect of where third-party candidate promises appear.

Analysis 2 – Promise Specificity

A second analysis asks whether third-party candidates differ from major-party candidates in their specificity of promises. This analysis uses probability models measuring each of the three variables tracking promise specificity. Because the first two variables, Policy/Action and Outcome, are binary, I used an ordinary least squares regression for each. Each of these two analyses determines the change in the probability of a statement having a Policy/Action or Outcome if a candidate is third-party compared to major-party. A logit regression was also used for the same purpose with the Timeline variable, chosen because only about 5% of promises have a Timeline, making it a rare occurrence.

Additionally, after examining each variable in isolation, I sought to probe the idea that, in combination, the presence of multiple variables implies greater specificity. Each promise can have one, two, or three variables present. Most promises contained only one of the three binary variables tracking specificity. However, some met two or all three of the criteria:

Table 8: How many promises met one, two, or all three of the specificity criteria

Variable Count	Meaning	Number of Promises	Percentage
1	Meets one criterion	1006	74.9%
2	Meets two criteria	324	24.1%
3	Meets all criteria	14	1.0%

This trend is still clearly visible when separated by party type:

Table 9: Percentage of major- and third-party promises that met one, two or all three of the specificity criteria

Party Type	Count = 1	Count = 2	Count = 3
Major party	71.4%	27.3%	1.4%
Third party	79.9%	19.5%	0.5%

To determine the probability of a given promise statement attaining a certain level of specificity between major and third parties, an ordered logit model was used to estimate two cutpoints (thresholds between levels) and predictor coefficients. Standard errors are clustered at the candidate level to account for the fact that promises from the same candidate are not independent of each other.

Table 10: Ordered logit model cutpoints between levels of promise specificity

Cutpoint	Estimate	SE (Clustered)
α_1 (1 vs. 2–3)	1.915	1.311
α_2 (1–2 vs. 3)	5.436	1.338

The large gap between α_1 (1.915) and α_2 (5.436) reflects the rarity of meeting all three criteria.

Table 11: Promise specificity regressions (clustered SEs in parentheses)

Variable	Policy/Action	Outcome	Timeline	Combined
(Intercept)	0.5208 (0.3179)	0.8111* (0.3424)	-11.4304*** (2.9074)	—
Third party	0.0059 (0.0689)	-0.0809 (0.0711)	-0.7592 (0.591)	-0.5062* (0.2067)
Log word count	0.0106 (0.0318)	-0.0127 (0.0336)	0.8995** (0.3026)	0.1353 (0.1446)
Format: Interview	0.0846 (0.0552)	-0.1244* (0.0615)	-0.5102 (0.601)	-0.3106 (0.2671)
Format: Town Hall	0.1201 (0.0944)	-0.184† (0.1045)	0.3794 (0.5887)	-0.1928 (0.348)
Format: Debate	0.0073 (0.1123)	0.2558 (0.1651)	-1.0923 (1.0769)	0.9817* (0.3885)
Medium: Article	-0.0316 (0.0885)	0.1376* (0.0671)	-0.8805* (0.4176)	0.4916† (0.2604)
Medium: Radio	-0.1854† (0.0975)	0.096 (0.1105)	—	-0.2285 (0.6802)
Medium: Video	0.0322 (0.0607)	0.055 (0.061)	-0.6917 (0.672)	0.4729 (0.3144)
Election year: 2004	0.2199*** (0.0474)	-0.0229 (0.047)	0.3237 (0.3207)	0.8692** (0.292)
Election year: 2008	0.3822*** (0.0729)	-0.294*** (0.0657)	1.0652 (0.6736)	0.6741* (0.3436)
Election year: 2012	0.1884** (0.0723)	-0.1517† (0.0865)	1.1722* (0.5002)	0.2948 (0.3534)
Election year: 2016	0.1573* (0.0717)	-0.131† (0.0774)	0.5193 (0.4118)	0.2005 (0.3222)
Election year: 2020	0.1363† (0.0753)	-0.1478* (0.0631)	-0.0687 (0.41)	-0.1985 (0.3483)
Election year: 2024	0.1027 (0.0791)	-0.0727 (0.0627)	0.333 (0.4455)	0.2395 (0.2745)
Gender: Female	0.044 (0.0557)	-0.046 (0.0594)	-1.3238** (0.4321)	-0.2144 (0.1807)
Race/Ethnicity: Black	-0.1484* (0.0702)	0.0983 (0.0639)	0.2031 (0.5032)	-0.3028 (0.2681)
Race/Ethnicity: Hispanic	-0.0529 (0.058)	-0.0457 (0.0601)	2.1945*** (0.6461)	-0.501 (0.5356)
Age	3e-04 (0.0022)	-0.0023 (0.0023)	0.0083 (0.0163)	-0.0068 (0.0071)

† $p < 0.10$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. Policy/Action and Outcome estimated with OLS; Timeline with logit; Combined with ordered logit. The Medium: Radio was dropped for the Timeline analysis, as no promises made via Radio included the Timeline variable.

Analyzing the individual models for the three measures of promise specificity shows there is no statistically significant difference between major- and third-party candidates. For the Policy/Action model, the coefficient of the third-party variable is 0.0059; for the Outcome model, it is -0.0809; and for the Timeline model it is -0.7592, none of which are statistically significant. This means third-party candidates are not significantly more or less likely than major-party candidates to make promises that include language implying a policy/action, outcome, or explicit timeline. However, the ordered logit model returns different results. After controlling for speech length, third-party candidates are significantly less likely to make promises that satisfy multiple specificity criteria simultaneously (coefficient = -0.506 , $p < 0.05$).

A strong effect seen in the combined model is that promises across parties made during the 2004 election were significantly more likely to satisfy multiple specificity criteria (coefficient = 0.869 , $p < 0.01$). However, accounting for this 2004 effect does not eliminate the difference between party types. The third-party coefficient in the combined model remains significant (coefficient = -0.506 , $p < 0.05$), suggesting that while the 2004 election inflated specificity levels overall, it does not fully explain the gap between major- and third-party candidates in combined specificity.

Interpretation

The individual specificity regressions show that third-party candidates do not differ significantly from major-party candidates on any single measure of promise specificity. While the second hypothesis predicted third-party promises would be more specific, the individual regressions instead show no significant difference, and the combined model points in the opposite direction. That prediction rested on two arguments: that third parties need specific

promises to build credibility with voters who have no reason to trust them yet (Bonilla 2024), and that they need clear positions to pressure major parties into responding to their issues (Adams and Merrill 2006). The data show that neither of these pressures actually pushes third-party specificity above major-party levels. A third-party promise is about as likely to contain an action or outcome as a major-party one, but it is not more likely to.

However, the fact that third parties match major parties on each individual criterion is itself worth noting. Third-party candidates operate with far fewer resources and far less institutional support, yet their promises still clear the same bar. This suggests that the credibility and agenda pressures described in the literature do exist, but that they only allow third parties to exist on the same playing field as major ones instead of granting them an advantage.

Third parties merely matching, not exceeding, the specificity of major parties could be explained by the same constraints identified in the promise count analysis: shorter appearances, fewer media opportunities, and the need to cover many issues in limited time. They restrict how much detail any individual promise can contain. While the need to establish credibility and influence the agenda increases specificity, these resource constraints hold it in place.

The ordered logit model highlights this tension. When the three specificity criteria are analyzed one at a time, major and third parties look the same. However, once speech length is held constant, third-party candidates are significantly less likely to incorporate multiple criteria into a single promise. In practice, this means a third-party candidate might clearly state a policy action but skip the projected outcome or the implementation timeline before moving on to the next topic. Major-party candidates, with more time and more appearances, can afford to develop each promise more fully by stating the policy, describing what it will achieve, and specifying when it will happen within the same statement.

This fits with Vavreck's (2009) argument that candidates facing strategic disadvantages need to be disciplined about how they spend their limited opportunities to communicate. If a third-party candidate has twenty minutes in a radio interview to cover their entire platform, it is more efficient to make ten less-specific promises across ten different issues than making five highly specific ones that miss half of their platform. The result is a strategy of breadth over depth.

Notably, the ordered logit model also identified a confounding effect from the 2004 election year, suggesting that promises made during the 2004 election cycle were significantly more likely to include multiple specificity criteria regardless of party type. One potential reason for this upwards shift is the policy landscape after the September 11, 2001 terrorist attacks. Heightened voter worries during this time may have influenced candidates to not only make targeted promises that might resolve the consequences of the attack but also make more specific promises across the board to ease voters' concerns.

Analysis 3 – Issue Emphasis

The third and final set of analyses concerns the issue categorization assigned to each statement. For each party, after taking a simple count of how many issues appeared for each party, Shannon entropy and evenness were measured. This measurement was taken at the party level rather than the candidate level to measure the impact of each party as a whole through all election cycles, not just the impact of individual candidates. Individual candidates may come and go, but party-level analysis demonstrates the collective emphasis of everyone who ran with that party.

Shannon entropy is a single number that captures two things at once: how many categories a party uses and how evenly it spreads its promises across those categories. If a party makes many promises, but about few topics, it would have a low entropy, but if it makes many promises across many topics it would have a high entropy. Evenness, or actual entropy divided by maximum entropy, was also calculated, which shows how evenly a party distributes its promises among the categories it addresses.

Table 12: Shannon entropy for each party

Party	Type	Promises	Categories Used	Entropy	Max Possible	Evenness
Republican	Major	414	32/36	4.368	5.000	0.874
Democrat	Major	382	31/36	4.134	4.954	0.834
Green	Third	150	24/36	4.135	4.585	0.902
Libertarian	Third	131	24/36	4.035	4.585	0.880
Independent	Third	108	29/36	4.543	4.858	0.935
Constitution	Third	38	17/36	3.735	4.087	0.914
Socialist USA	Third	31	12/36	3.321	3.585	0.926
PSL	Third	23	13/36	3.534	3.700	0.955
Reform	Third	22	11/36	3.266	3.459	0.944
Peace & Freedom	Third	18	12/36	3.461	3.585	0.966
Justice	Third	7	3/36	1.379	1.585	0.870
Legal MJ Now	Third	7	4/36	1.842	2.000	0.921
America's	Third	6	5/36	2.252	2.322	0.970
Soc. Equality	Third	3	3/36	1.585	1.585	1.000
Soc. Workers	Third	2	2/36	1.000	1.000	1.000
Solidarity	Third	2	2/36	1.000	1.000	1.000

In terms of raw entropy, which is heavily influenced by sample size, Republicans (4.368) and Democrats (4.134) have the highest because they have the most promises (414 and 382), allowing them to cover more categories. Among third parties, Independents (4.543) have the highest raw entropy of any party, but they also have 108 promises, one of the highest promise counts among third parties. The smallest parties (Solidarity and Socialist Workers, each with 2 promises) have entropy near 1.0 simply because they can only cover 2 categories.

Evenness is more revealing because it removes the sample size effect. ‘Perfect’ evenness, a value of 1.0, means promises are distributed equally among the areas a candidate covers. Here the pattern reverses. The Democrats have the lowest evenness of any party (0.834), meaning they concentrate their promises most unevenly: 17% of promises are dedicated to healthcare and 15% to education, with other areas not receiving nearly as much content.

Among small parties, several achieve perfect or near-perfect evenness (Soc. Equality: 1.000, Peace & Freedom: 0.966, America's: 0.970). However, this is less meaningful because they have so few promises that such an outcome is nearly inevitable.

Table 13: Pooled Shannon entropy for major versus third parties

Group	Promises	Categories Used	Entropy	Evenness
Major parties (pooled)	796	33/36	4.367	0.866
Third parties (pooled)	548	35/36	4.524	0.882

The aggregate comparison shows that third parties pooled together, with an entropy of 4.524 and evenness of 0.882, are slightly more diverse than major parties pooled together, with an entropy of 4.367 and evenness of 0.866. This happens because each third party makes its own niche of issues: Libertarians have taxes; Greens have the environment; Socialists have foreign policy. Because there is not a lot of overlap between these areas, the collective coverage by all third parties together is broader than the coverage by both major parties together.

Breaking the data down by individual party supports this idea that each has a unique issue profile.

Table 14: The top three issue categories for parties with 18 or more promises in the dataset

Party	Promise Count	Top 3 Categories (% share)
Republican	414	Healthcare (12.6%), Immigration (11.6%), Taxes (8.2%)
Democrat	382	Healthcare (17.0%), Education (14.9%), Taxes (10.5%)
Green	150	Environment (12.0%), Education (12.0%), Healthcare (10.0%)
Libertarian	131	Taxes (19.8%), Gov't reform (9.2%), Drug policy (7.6%)
Independent	108	Healthcare (12.0%), Environment (7.4%), Immigration (6.5%)
Constitution	38	Immigration (15.8%), Education (13.2%), Gov't reform (13.2%)
Socialist USA	31	Foreign policy (19.4%), Gov't reform (16.1%), Healthcare (12.9%)
PSL	23	Gov't reform (17.4%), Foreign policy (13.0%), Multiple at 8.7%
Reform	22	Environment (18.2%), Economy (13.6%), Immigration (13.6%)
Peace & Freedom	18	Education (16.7%), Multiple at 11.1%

Parties with fewer than 18 promises should be interpreted with caution, as their entropy and evenness are heavily influenced by individual promise coding decisions. For example, while Legal Marijuana Now (7 promises, 43% drug policy) and Justice Party (7 promises, 57% elections) appear very concentrated in certain areas, this is only on account of having so few promises that small changes in coding create large changes in distribution.

There are some notable patterns across parties. Healthcare is a top issue for nearly every party, but Democrats devote 17% versus Republicans at 12.6% and Libertarians at just 7.6%. Immigration is divided along partisan lines: Republicans (11.6%) and Constitution Party (15.8%) make it a top priority, while Democrats dedicate only 1.0%. Drug policy is a priority for Libertarians (7.6%) and Greens (5.3%) but receives 0% from Democrats and only 1.2% from Republicans. Libertarians are unique in devoting nearly one-fifth of all promises to taxes (19.8%), more than double any other party. Socialist parties (Socialist USA and PSL) are the only ones where foreign policy and government reform are the top two categories. Only Democrats emphasize wages and workers' rights (5.8%) and childcare (2.1%) substantially. These categories receive minimal or zero attention from most third parties.

Given that third parties collectively cover a broader range of topics, a question arises about why this breadth occurs. One possibility is that individual third-party candidates each focus on a small number of niche issues, and the broad collective coverage is simply the sum of many narrow platforms covering different areas. An alternative explanation is that individual third-party candidates are not actually narrower than major-party candidates, but instead maintain similarly broad platforms while distributing their promises across different topics. To distinguish between these explanations, a supplementary analysis tested whether party type predicts the number of issues an individual candidate covers after controlling for total promise count.

Both simple topic count and Shannon entropy were used as dependent variables for another ordinary least squares regression, as these variables both measure how broad a given candidate's platform is. The independent variable was party type, either major or third. If party type is still statistically significant after controlling for promise count, it suggests any difference in breadth noted in third parties is not merely an artifact of them making fewer promises, but instead actually relates to candidates being third-party.

This analysis was restricted to candidates with 5 or more promises, as only those candidates can meaningfully demonstrate breadth or narrowness. Candidates with fewer than 5 promises will inherently have, at maximum, 4 categories, and most likely fewer. Limiting analysis to 5 promises or more still allows 46 candidates to be analyzed.

Table 15: OLS regression predicting number of policy topics covered by candidate

Variable	Coefficient	Std Error	t-statistic	p-value
(Intercept)	-0.7317	4.9449	-0.148	0.8831
promise_count	0.1757***	0.0147	11.913	0.0000
third_party	-0.4021	0.8434	-0.477	0.6360
avg_log_words	0.8084	0.5825	1.388	0.1725

$R^2 = 0.827$, $Adjusted R^2 = 0.814$, $N = 46$, $F = 66.71$.

† $p < 0.10$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

This model shows that, with a coefficient of 0.1757 and a p-value of <0.001, the number of promises a candidate makes is a powerful predictor of how many categories they cover. With a negative coefficient of -0.4021 and a large p-value of 0.6360, being a third-party candidate has no significant additional effect. The average log word count of a candidate's materials also does not significantly predict topic coverage, with a coefficient of 0.8084 and a p-value of 0.1725. The model's adjusted R^2 of 0.814 indicates that these variables together explain 81% of the variation in the number of policy topics covered.

Another ordinary least-squares regression was performed with Shannon entropy as the dependent variable instead.

Table 16: OLS regression predicting Shannon entropy per candidate

Variable	Coefficient	Std Error	t-statistic	p-value
(Intercept)	0.875	0.7353	1.190	0.2407
promise_count	0.0108***	0.0022	4.946	0.0000
third_party	-0.0431	0.1254	-0.343	0.7330
avg_log_words	0.1069	0.0866	1.234	0.2242

$R^2 = 0.475$, $Adjusted R^2 = 0.438$, $N = 46$, $F = 12.69$.

† $p < 0.10$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Similarly, with a coefficient of 0.0108 and another very small p-value of <0.001 , number of promises made is also a significant predictor of Shannon entropy. Party type again does not make a statistically significant difference, with a negative coefficient of -0.0431 and a large p-value of 0.7330. Additionally, average log word count is not a significant predictor, with a coefficient of 0.1069 and a p-value of 0.2242. This means the appearance of individual third-party candidates having narrower campaign platforms is almost entirely a side effect of their smaller sample size.

Interpretation

The party-level breakdown reveals that each party has a distinct issue fingerprint, a combination of issues associated with that party. This supports the theoretical arguments drawn from saliency theory and issue ownership: parties compete not only by taking positions on shared issues, but by choosing which issue areas to foreground. The evidence suggests third-party candidates use their promises less to replicate the dominant major-party agenda and more to redirect attention toward issues, or combinations of issues, that major parties underemphasize. Libertarians, for example, devoted nearly one-fifth of their promises to taxes, more than double any other party, while also being the only party to make drug policy a top-three priority. Socialist parties were unique in placing foreign policy and government reform at the center of their platforms. These patterns are consistent with selective emphasis: each party prioritizes issues aligned with its ideology rather than attempting to match the Republican or Democratic agenda.

The pooled entropy comparison also shows that third parties collectively cover a broader total range of issues than major parties, confirming the third hypothesis. This supports the claim that third parties function as agenda-expanding actors within presidential politics. Because

different third parties come from different ideological traditions and bring different neglected issues into the campaign, the combined effect of their participation is to widen the total issue space addressed during elections. The role of third parties in U.S. elections therefore cannot be fully understood by examining any single third party in isolation. It is the collective efforts of many ideologically diverse third parties that broadens the range of issues at stake during election cycles.

One natural explanation for this collective breadth would be that each third party focuses narrowly on a small set of niche issues, and the broad coverage is simply the sum of many narrow platforms spanning different areas. If this were the case, individual third-party candidates should cover fewer issues than individual major-party candidates even after accounting for promise count. However, the supplementary candidate-level analysis does not support this interpretation. After controlling for total promise count, party type did not significantly predict either the number of unique topic categories a candidate covered or candidate-level Shannon entropy. A third-party candidate who makes 20 promises covers roughly as many issues as a major-party candidate who also makes 20 promises. The apparent narrowness of individual third-party platforms in the raw data is thus a product of their lower volume, not of a more concentrated platform strategy.

This is an important correction to the common assumption that outsider candidates are single-issue and advance narrow programs. Niche party theory and issue entrepreneurship both suggest that third-party candidates should concentrate their efforts on a limited number of salient issues, which might lead one to expect individually narrower platforms even after controlling for promise count. Instead, the evidence suggests that third-party candidates maintain broad platforms while distributing their emphasis differently from major-party candidates. They are not

narrower in scope, just different in focus. The broader collective coverage identified above therefore arises not from many specialists combining to fill the issue space, but from many broadly engaged candidates each weighing their agendas toward different topics.

Discussion

Table 17: Whether the three hypotheses on third-party promise-making strategy were validated

Hypothesis	Text	Validated?
1	Third-party presidential candidates make fewer promise statements per speech than major-party presidential candidates.	Yes
2	Third-party presidential candidates' promise statements are more specific than those of major-party presidential candidates.	No
3	The distribution of promises across issues differs significantly between individual major- and third-party candidates.	Yes

This thesis aimed to explain how campaign promise-making differs between major-party and third-party presidential candidates in the United States. Rather than examining only whether promises are fulfilled, it asked whether party type is associated with differences in promise frequency, specificity, and issue emphasis. The analyses tested three hypotheses across these dimensions, with a supplementary analysis examining the mechanism behind collective topic breadth. Across all dimensions, the results point toward a clear overall pattern: third-party candidates do not appear to be less serious or less developed rhetorical actors than major-party candidates. Instead, they differ most clearly in how often they make promises and in which issues they choose to emphasize.

Taken together, the findings support a reinterpretation of third-party presidential rhetoric. Third-party candidates are neither miniature versions of major-party candidates nor merely vague protest figures. They make fewer promises, and the promises they do make are comparably specific on individual measures, though less likely to combine multiple specificity criteria. They emphasize different issues than major parties, and when combined, they expand the range of issues represented in presidential campaigns. At the same time, individual third-party candidates do not appear to have narrower platforms than major-party candidates once promise count is accounted for, suggesting that their different emphasis is a matter of focus

rather than scope. The most accurate way to describe third-party candidates is therefore as agenda-differentiating actors, candidates who intervene in presidential politics by bringing neglected issues to the forefront and showcasing unique combinations of policy priorities, even when they are unlikely to win office.

Limitations and Future Research

One key limitation of this study is its sample size. The materials collected only extend as far back as 2000, mostly due to the difficulty of finding campaign materials from third parties before that date. Major-party candidates simply had more appearances to sample from, leading to them being more represented in the dataset. Often, third-party candidates received one or no interviews from larger media organizations, and more often appeared on smaller radio shows or amateur online videos. In contrast, major party candidates never appeared outside of major news outlets or curated archives of their past speeches, a luxury unable to be afforded to third parties. For these reasons, major parties received comparatively more entries in the database, making it necessary to account for this difference carefully in my analysis.

Several other limitations exist within the data. I hand-coded all data, and the lack of additional coders is a missing check on the soundness of my coding decisions. Though the rules for coding described in the Methods section were applied during the coding process, data classification must involve some extent of interpretive judgment. Additional research may incorporate new and multiple coders, together with measures of inter-coder reliability, to limit the impact of such judgment on the results.

Moreover, the binary specificity measures included in this dataset may not be sufficient to capture how detailed or specific promises are. While tracking three variables of specificity

eliminates much of the subjectivity surrounding the concept, that subjectivity brings with it a complexity that can be examined in future research. Instead of or in combination with coded data, survey data could supplement the understanding of what makes a promise specific or vague.

Beyond these limitations, future research could build on this project in several ways. Extending the analysis time frame farther back, especially to earlier high-profile third-party campaigns, could test whether these patterns hold historically. Another option would be to compare campaign speeches, interviews, and other live candidate appearances with more impersonal material such as party platforms and advertisements to see whether third-party agenda differentiation appears consistently across communication formats. It would also be useful to study whether major parties later adopt, ignore, or attack the issues third parties emphasize, which would more strongly test the claim that outsider candidates act as agenda entrepreneurs. Finally, future work could examine whether certain categories of third parties, such as ideological, protest, or candidate-centered campaigns, differ from one another in promise specificity and issue emphasis.

Conclusion

Across three analyses of 1,344 promise statements spanning seven election cycles, the central finding of this thesis is that third-party presidential candidates are best understood as agenda-differentiating actors. They are not vague protest figures running on slogans, nor are they miniature versions of major-party candidates with thinner platforms. When a third-party candidate makes a promise, that promise is about as likely to include a concrete policy action, an identifiable outcome, or an explicit timeline as one made by a Democrat or Republican. Though their promises may be fewer in number, they are not less robust in substance.

Where third-party candidates diverge is in which issues they choose to address. Each party in the dataset displayed a distinct issue fingerprint. Libertarians devoted nearly a fifth of their promises to taxes, Socialist parties centered their platforms around foreign policy and government reform, and the Green Party focused on the environment and education. These were not priorities of Republican or Democratic campaign speeches. When pooled together, third-party candidates covered a broader and more evenly distributed range of topics than both major parties combined, not because each individual candidate ran a narrow single-issue campaign, but because many candidates with broader platforms each had agendas that highlighted different areas.

The pattern examined here matters for democratic debate beyond the question of who wins. If presidential campaigns are understood only as contests between two major-party nominees, then the issues that receive sustained public attention are decided almost entirely by those two candidates and the media environment that surrounds them. Drug policy, election reform, civil liberties, and criminal justice, all topics that appeared prominently in third-party

promises, might otherwise go largely undiscussed during an election cycle. Over time, some of these issues have moved towards major-party platforms, suggesting that third-party promises can shape political discourse beyond the cycle in which they first appear.

The study of campaign promises has long centered on whether politicians follow through on what they say during elections. This thesis suggests that an equally important question is who gets to make promises in the first place, and about what. In a political system structurally biased against them, third-party candidates persist in making promises that differ not in specificity but in subject matter. That persistence, and the agenda expansion it produces, is a meaningful form of political participation that deserves closer attention from scholars of American politics.

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Appendix I – List of Promise Issues

This list was inspired by Gallup’s Most Important Problem survey. It categorizes candidate promise statements into the following issues, ordered by their frequency in the database:

1. Healthcare (166)
2. Education (126)
3. Taxes (117)
4. Environment & energy (107)
5. Immigration & border security (87)
6. Government spending, debt & reform (76)
7. Foreign policy & diplomacy (58)
8. Infrastructure (53)
9. Wages & workers' rights (49)
10. Military & defense (44)
11. Jobs & employment (43)
12. Social Security & retirement (36)
13. Crime & criminal justice (36)
14. Wars & military intervention (33)
15. Drug policy (32)
16. Abortion & reproductive rights (31)
17. Economy (general) (30)
18. Elections & campaign finance (29)
19. Trade & tariffs (28)

20. Civil liberties, privacy & free speech (22)
21. Housing (20)
22. Welfare & poverty (19)
23. LGBTQ+ rights (14)
24. Gun policy (14)
25. Racial justice & civil rights (13)
26. Childcare & family policy (12)
27. Cost of living & inflation (9)
28. Anti-DEI & anti-woke policy (9)
29. Courts & judicial appointments (8)
30. General governance & leadership (7)
31. Culture, faith & values (6)
32. Wealth inequality & corporate power (5)
33. Veterans affairs (2)
34. Food & agriculture (1)
35. Space & science (1)
36. Disaster response (1)

Appendix II – Heatmap of Issue Coverage Percentages by Party

Category	Republican	Democrat	Green	Libertarian	Independent	Constitution	Socialist USA	PSL	Reform	Peace & Freedom
Economy (general)	2.7	0.8	0.7	4.6	1.9	—	—	8.7	13.6	5.6
Cost of living & inflation	1	1	—	—	0.9	—	—	—	—	—
Government spending, debt & reform	6.5	3.4	3.3	9.2	4.6	13.2	16.1	17.4	—	—
Jobs & employment	5.8	3.4	—	—	2.8	2.6	—	4.3	4.5	—
Taxes	8.2	10.5	2.7	19.8	3.7	10.5	6.5	4.3	4.5	—
Trade & tariffs	3.1	1	1.3	2.3	2.8	—	3.2	—	9.1	—
Wages & workers' rights	1.2	5.8	4.7	—	5.6	2.6	6.5	8.7	—	11.1
Wealth inequality & corporate power	—	0.3	—	—	2.8	—	—	—	—	—
Abortion & reproductive rights	2.2	1.8	0.7	5.3	1.9	5.3	—	—	—	5.6
Childcare & family policy	0.2	2.1	—	—	—	2.6	3.2	—	4.5	—
Drug policy	1.2	—	5.3	7.6	3.7	—	—	—	—	—
Food & agriculture	—	—	0.7	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Healthcare	12.6	17	10	7.6	12	2.6	12.9	4.3	9.1	11.1
Housing	1	1.8	3.3	0.8	1.9	—	—	—	—	5.6
Social Security & retirement	2.2	3.4	3.3	0.8	4.6	2.6	6.5	—	—	—
Welfare & poverty	1.2	1.8	—	1.5	0.9	2.6	—	—	—	—
Civil liberties, privacy & free speech	1.2	0.5	6	0.8	2.8	5.3	—	—	—	—
LGBTQ+ rights	1.7	1	—	1.5	—	—	—	—	—	5.6
Racial justice & civil rights	0.5	1.8	0.7	0.8	0.9	—	—	4.3	—	—
Anti-DEI & anti-woke policy	1.9	—	—	—	—	2.6	—	—	—	—
Culture, faith & values	0.5	0.8	—	—	0.9	—	—	—	—	—
Courts & judicial appointments	0.7	0.3	—	0.8	1.9	2.6	—	—	—	—
Crime & criminal justice	1.9	1.6	7.3	2.3	5.6	—	—	4.3	—	5.6
Elections & campaign finance	0.7	1.3	4.7	1.5	5.6	—	—	—	—	—
Gun policy	1.2	1.8	—	0.8	0.9	—	—	—	—	—
General governance & leadership	0.5	0.5	—	—	2.8	—	—	—	—	—

Education	7.7	14.9	12	3.8	3.7	13.2	—	—	4.5	16.7
Space & science	—	—	0.7	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Disaster response	—	—	0.7	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Infrastructure	4.1	3.7	2	3.1	3.7	7.9	9.7	8.7	13.6	—
Environment & energy	6.5	9.7	12	4.6	7.4	5.3	3.2	8.7	18.2	5.6
Foreign policy & diplomacy	4.1	2.9	2.7	6.9	4.6	2.6	19.4	13	4.5	5.6
Immigration & border security	11.6	1	6	4.6	6.5	15.8	—	—	13.6	11.1
Military & defense	3.6	1.8	4.7	3.8	1.9	—	9.7	8.7	—	11.1
Veterans affairs	0.2	0.3	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Wars & military intervention	2.2	1.8	4.7	5.3	0.9	—	3.2	4.3	—	—

The shading scale goes from 0% (no shading) to 20% (most shading).

— indicates no promises were made on that issue by that party.